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accept

active **c**ommunities & **e**nergy
prosumers for the energy **t**ransition

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER 957781

WP9 – Outreach activities for impact enhancement

D9.1 – ACCEPT branding, website and social media channels

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AUTHORS

Name	Organisation	e-mail	Role
Sebastian Koch	EEE	s.koch@eee-info.net	Leading Author

REVIEWERS

Name	Organisation	e-mail
Pablo Barrachina	MIWenergia	Pablo.barrachina@miwenergia.com
Stelios Genouzos	Witside	Stelios.genouzos@witside.com

VERSION HISTORY

Version	Date	Comments
1.0	11.3.21	1 st Draft version
1.1	31.3.21	Final Version

PROJECT CONSORTIUM

Austria

- European Center for Renewable Energy Güssing GmbH

Cyprus

- Witside International Markets LTD

Denmark

- Geco Global APS

Greece

- **Hypertech** (Project Coordinator)
- Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis
- Mytilinaios Anonimi Etaireia
- QUE Technologies Kefalaiiouchiki Etaireia

Ireland

- University College Cork
- National University of Ireland, Cork

Italy

- Rina Consulting SPA

Netherlands

- Bedrijfsbureau Energie Samen BV
- Cooperatief Energie Dienstenbedrijfs Rivierenland BA

Spain

- My Energia Oner SL
- La Solar Energia Sociedad Cooperativa
- Fundacion Undacion Circe Centre De Investigacion de Recursos Y Consumos Energeticos
- Viesgo Distribucion Electrica SL

Switzerland

- Azienda Elettrica Di Massagno SA

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Grid integration of variable renewable energy sources poses major challenges with respect to system stability due to demand-supply imbalances. Energy communities are emerging as a promising element to promote citizen involvement in the energy transition. However, ICT tools are required to extract and optimise the flexibility of residential energy resources to create financially viable operations based on citizen needs.

The EU-funded ACCEPT project intends to develop and deliver such a digital toolbox that allows energy communities to offer innovative digital services and access revenue streams that can financially support their functions and secure their sustainability and effectiveness. The ACCEPT framework will be demonstrated and validated in four pilot sites in Greece, the Netherlands, Spain and Switzerland involving more than 3000 people and 750 residences.

For the best possible communication of the project's process, activities and results to the general public as well as an optimal stakeholder engagement, within this deliverable it is important to predetermine tools, guidelines and standards of communication for all project partners to refer to during the course of the project.

This deliverable gives an overview of the ACCEPT branding design, the website development and all social media dissemination channels.

Section 2 of the deliverable gives an insight on the process of formation of the project logo as well as guidelines on how to properly use the project name in further communication with project partners, the general public and stakeholders.

Section 3 focusses on the development of the project website, which went online by the end of March, 2021. It gives insights on the website's contents and the structure, as well as information about the preliminary website, that had been online since the beginning of February 2021.

The project's Social Media channels, which are stated in section 4 should support the project team to engage, inform and interact with stakeholders and the general public.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and objectives of deliverable

This deliverable features the setting up of the first dissemination and communication tools, guidelines and standards of communication for all project partners to refer to during the course of the project for the best possible communication of the project's process, activities and results to the general public as well as an optimal stakeholder engagement which is essential to the project's success.

1.2. Structure of deliverables

This deliverable is an independent document, but it hands the foundation of the ACCEPT project's Dissemination and Communication plan and activity reports:

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

Needless to say, the dissemination and communication of the project have direct relation to all other tasks and work packages, as these guidelines are part of almost all project activities.

2. Project Branding

2.1. Logo

The logo draft was created by the project partner **European Center for Renewable Energy Guessing** and presented to the project consortium within the process of the project submission phase. The proposal was adopted by the project consortium.

2.2. Symbolism

To perfectly represent & communicate the topics of the project with the project logo, the logo design includes 3 eye-catching symbolisms:

- **a community**
symbolized by a group of 3 people
- **prosumer**
symbolized by 2 separate persons
- **energy**
symbolized by the standard off/on-icon above the e, which itself is representative of the word "energy"

2.3. Colours

The design of the project logo is laid out in a modern and also soft colorway, to give the audience a relation to the keywords of the project:

- Energy
- Community
- Transition
- Change
- Vision
- Future

celery

C	22
M	0
Y	49
K	21
R	157
G	201
B	103
#9dc967	

jungle

C	75
M	0
Y	8
K	31
R	44
G	177
B	163
#2cb1a3	

downy

C	57
M	5
Y	0
K	18
R	89
G	198
B	208
#59c6d0	

abbey

C	3
M	2
Y	0
K	64
R	88
G	89
B	91
#58595b	

2.4. Logogram

For the best possible communication of the project's message, the abbreviation of ACCEPT, **a**ctive **c**ommunities & **e**nergy **p**rosomers for the energy **t**ransition is part of the logo design.

2.5. Wording

The official wording of the project is

ACCEPT – **a**ctive **c**ommunities & **e**nergy **p**rosomers for the energy **t**ransition

“ACCEPT” in capital letters, subtitle in lower case letters and – if possible – the abbreviating letters written in bold.

3. Website

3.1. Preliminary Website

For the purpose of giving project partners as well as stakeholders and the general public a chance to contact the project consortium, follow the project's social media channels (Point 3) and get to know the project partners, a preliminary website was implemented.

The preliminary website was presented to the project consortium at the 1st plenary telco on Monday, February 1st and accessible from that point on at:

www.accept-project.eu

The preliminary website contained:

- Links to the project's social media channels
- A link to send an email to the dissemination & communication leader of the project
- A link to the project's repository for the project consortium
- All project partner logos linked to the respective partner websites
- The EU-Emblem for the H2020-programme
- Legal Notice and Privacy Policy

ACCEPT preliminary website welcome page

ACCEPT preliminary website display of project partners

3.2. Official project website launch

By the end of march, the preliminary website was replaced with the official project website and introduced to all the partners in the monthly plenary.

3.3. Website structure

3.4. Website content

3.4.1. Project news

Current activities in the project and other project-relevant news

3.4.2. Events

Project events and other project-relevant international events

3.4.3. About the project

Project introduction and description of the workpackages

3.4.4. Consortium

Project partner logos with respective subpages with information about the PPs, which was obtained in advance from the PPs via an online form:

- PP Logo
- PP Description
- PP's Role in the project
- Web- and social media links
- Location

PROJECT PARTNER FORM

Dear ACCEPT project partners,
for the implementation of your company in the ACCEPT project website, we would like you to fill out the following form with your company details.

Company name *

Company short description (less than 750 characters) *

Short description of role in the project (less than 500 characters) *

Company address *

Company location (coordinates) *

Company website *

Social media channel 1

Social media channel 2

Social media channel 3

Social media channel 4

SEND

Online project partner form

3.4.5. Living labs

Description of the living labs and location of the pilot sites

3.4.6. Library

Public Dissemination material and media

3.4.7. Legal Notice

3.4.8. Privacy Policy

3.4.9. Footer

- Social media links
- Newsletter registration form
- Twitter feed
- Contact information
- EU emblem and project disclaimer
- Bridge link

ACCEPT website footer

4. Social Media Channels

For the best possible outreach to stakeholders and the general public, the following social media channels were established:

4.1. Twitter

ACCEPT project Twitter page

4.2. LinkedIn

ACCEPT project LinkedIn page

4.3. Youtube

ACCEPT project Youtube channel